

Developing Product Brand Value in Response to Customer Satisfaction Participation in Building and Customer. Experience Management.

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Abstract: This article is for synthetic purposes. Conceptual framework for developing brand value in dimensions to respond to customer needs Participation in building and customer experience management Using theoretical synthesis and related research Developed into a conceptual framework that consists of various factors, namely customer participation. Customer experience management Customer cooperation management and customer satisfaction. Which leads to the development of brand value There are five main components: brand awareness. Perceived quality Brand group Brand image and brand loyalty Developing successful brand values. Business organizations must consider 3 main factors: customer participation. Customer experience management and cooperation management with customers This research framework has an influence to promote and develop brand value in terms of meeting customer needs.

Keywords: customer engagement, Customer experience management, customer cooperation management, customer satisfaction

I. Introduction

The business of producing products to meet the needs of consumers in the digital age resulting from the rapid technology development. Operators must consider marketing strategies that are appropriate for each era. That are different with results from technology or competitors on the same production line Therefore, each era of marketing is different. Therefore, each era of marketing is different. Caused by continuous product development in the past, it was a production-oriented market in order to keep pace with customer demand, where production was mainly focused on quantity. And consumers are still not connected in technology. Therefore, the manufacturer or business groups therefore focus on producing the products that they want to produce in the market Then use the method to set policies for salespeople They tried to sell their own products (Cohen et al., 2006, p. 261), but with more competition they started. Along with the consumers it can be connected with each other by technology. Wider aspect of social communication and create a network that shares experiences gained from product consumption Businesses therefore have to switch to a customer centric strategy with the main intent of: Product improvement and sales promotion to meet the needs of the most customers.(Dennis &Kambil, 2003, p.45) As a result, marketers have to research customer needs. And then used to design and forward to the production process to get the product according to the customer most Which is loyalty to the brand This is called loyalty, both in an attitude and a behavior.(Kumar et al., 2008; Ryals, 2008, p. 323)

II. Objective

The purpose of this article is to synthesize the conceptual framework. These include various factors that affect the development of brand value.

III. Expected benefits

In order to get a conceptual framework for promoting, implementing and developing brand values This will affect customer satisfaction leading to the development of brand value.

IV. How to conduct the study

This article is conducted by reviewing relevant literature, theories and research. To find the factors that affect customer satisfaction. For the development of brand value and synthesis as a conceptual framework Along with a summary of the results in order to get a guideline for applying to the product brand value development plan in the future.

V. Literature review

Brand Equity has been described in a variety of academic works, for example, Schiffman & Kanuk (2007) said that brand value refers to the value inherent in a brand that consumers accept in meeting their needs. Quality "Customer Based Brand Equity", the brand value is what happens in the mind of the customer. Due to the knowledge and understanding of the target customers Therefore, the brand value is a reflection of the effectiveness of a business' brand marketing operation. In which the customer experiences the feeling. From that brand, different levels of perception affect different types of responses, which can be both positive and negative. Positive merchant perceptions demonstrate love, affection. Connect and develop good products, create favor and lead to loyalty. Positive merchandise bags are valuable benefits both at the micro level (Micro). And Macro (Kotler & Keller (2012), backed by historical research by Bovee, Houston & Thill (1995) that say that if customers perceive brand value positively, it is a tangible asset. Not of that business (Aaker, 1996)

Importance of Brand Value Farquhar (1989) has stated that brand value is It is added value to the company, store or consumer. This is the relationship between the brand and customer behavior that affects the sales of the Company's products. Brand value can be measured from the cash flow that has increased by the presence of all brands of the product. This is the result of setting a price higher than its competitors. Cost reduction in marketing promotion activities And the increase in market share (Incremental Cash Flow) goal of adding value to the brand. There are two main reasons for this: to allow businesses to set a price for a brand if a deal occurs. To add intangible assets to the balance sheet. In addition, brand value is beneficial to the business of producing and distributing new products. And help in brand management for flexibility If an entity is in crisis, it also acts as a protection against new competitors entering the market (Kotler, 2012).

Composition of Brand Equity

Brand Equity is a concept that was presented and evolved in the 1980s Hardin & Keller (1988), which played an important role in the success of a wide variety of products and services. It is also an important issue in promoting and fostering good relationships among marketing organizations. Keller (1998) stated that brand value Caused by designing products that understand the customer. Making it able to meet the needs of consumers of the same group By the nuances that are distinguished by this requirement It may be able to be touched physically or emotionally. Create a sense of brand value Aaker's study (1996) divides the components of a product / service that leads to brand value awareness into five parts: 1) Brand Awareness 2) Perceived Quality 3) Brand Associations 4.) Brand Image and 5) Brand Loyalty.

Factors affecting the development of product brand value in terms of meeting customer needs. Many scholars have the opinion that to create customer needs for the development of brand value in dimensions to respond to customer needs. There are factors to consider:

Customer engagement started to study in the year. 1980 by Toffler (1980); Toffler (1983); Gronroos (1990); Gummesson (1991); Davidow & Malone (1992); Pine (1993). From various dimensions that the customer wants per product in response to satisfaction and building ties. This way of thinking is the source of the contemporary logic in doing business. To manage matters successfully, it requires cooperation from the customer in the production chain (Solweig Wikstrom, 1995, pp.6-19). With both direct and indirect business in terms of revenue and knowledge that is beneficial to the business at a low cost.

Components of customer engagement the use of customer relationship strategies, both to deliberately see results from consumption, barriers, usage Including the importance of improving the product to have a characteristic that responds to consumers. Classified as valuable knowledge to lead to sustainable business practice. This is an important function that marketers must contribute to making this happen. In this regard, the information needed from customers in terms of attitude and behavior are all influencing the adaptation of the entire business process. Can respond effectively Some businesses also implement this strategy. And successful loyalty with customers (Wikstrom and Lundkvist, 1995) such as laundry and another example of good business success is. Japanese automobile industry in the early stages, there were

rewards for salespeople who did not only make sales. However, customer knowledge of the purchased vehicle can be returned to the company for analysis in response to such demand (Womack et al., 1990).

Customer experience management means A business idea that can help a business be a customer-first organization. And deliver outstanding and personalized customer experiences. In today's digital world When a customer has multiple channels and touchpoints to access a product It is even more important to deliver the first customer experience in every interaction. By covering the whole physical experience and not physical, for example Brand awareness the presence of new discoveries in the product. Emphasizing the brand in a sense Customer brand loyalty (Randall, 2000) requires an element of the 3 aspects of the brand image are the symbolic image. Image of use and emotional image. Perceived emotions can be positive or negative. This is because the image of the product is caused by the management of the business owner (Verhoef et al., 2009), having a positive image will benefit the owner of the product. When so Thus a marketing concept called Customer experience management, which is the process of converting the business strategy of managing the relevant customer experience with the product in order to benefit the business in fostering relationships. To lead to product loyalty. (Schmitt, 2010, p24) Frow and Payne (2007), a technology expert to explain that businesses need to be able to understand customer needs by creating products. That was beyond expectations until the customer became the target 'Brand advocacy', Gentile et al. (2007).

The importance of managing the customer experience From historical research data on the issue of marketing management, it was found that the topic of customer experience management. A study of 362 companies in the United States (Rajgopal, 2000) was studied, with 80 percent believing that they were able to manage the so-called "Superior experience" experience for their clients. Which influences the persistence of the customer Customer experience from being involved in the use of marketing strategies. To make products with different attributes to meet the needs of customers. Until the effect on both physical perception and the emotional state of consumers (Gentile et al., 2007).

Cooperation management with customers It is developed by taking the concept that is customer oriented (Customer Oriented) by wanting to meet customer needs up to the internal level (Customer Insight). Customer coproducer is proactive management. In the past, customer coproducer was considered a "proactive management". Passive Management (Solveig Wikstrom, 1995, p. 14-15) because when the owner of the product is introduced, it will develop or design as the customer suggests. But nowadays, cooperation management with customers (Collaborative Management) It is the duty of marketers to support and promote through all forms of communication, including the use of computer technology to assist customers in designing products that meet their needs. Guidelines for handling cooperation with customers. It is therefore something that has been used to solve the problem of customer needs in many organizations. In order to meet customer satisfaction in products / services, Agranoff & McGuire (2003, p. 4) defines customer collaboration means "building a relationship between the company that owns the product with the customer with the aim of creating a relationship between the company that owns the product and the customer." Obtained will receive a message indicating the need to design a product to meet the needs of the customer, leading to a feeling of satisfaction in the product / service Later when it receives the desired updates. Taking this point of view in a strategic marketing by Thomson & Perry (2006) has meant that customer collaboration is: Marketing strategies used in response to the main customers or target groups It is a way to meet individual or group needs to meet the needs of individual or individual customers. In order to make customers satisfied with products / services And it leads to loyalty to the service and the product. Meaning in this story McGuire (2006) expands that the management of collaboration with customers. It is the integration of electronic business tools to coordinate with working processes in marketing and production departments. To perfectly support the consumer's consumption or use of customer service.

The concept of managing cooperation with customers. It is a relationship management (Relational Management) between the company that produces the products and the customers. Which is deeper Customer Relationship Management (CRM) where customers need to be aware of and express themselves as well, helping to design products / services that they expect to be appropriate. This process characterizes the process of communicating with customers to assess relationships (Interaction and Exchange) And use this relationship to benefit the business Effective customer collaboration is the excellence of marketing management. This is because managing this issue is a complex matter but is valuable for applying knowledge to managing the production chain. The marketers who coordinate this partnership with the client need to have a plan for building a partnership from the outside society where the customer comes into the organization. Managing successful customer collaboration will be the driving force behind the success of the organization (Beth, Chris & Simon, 2017). Customer collaboration knowledge is the economic value that can be gained from the reduction. Cost and purchase are the values in bringing that knowledge to competitive innovation. In a stable organization, there will be multilateral relationships with all units involved in the production and distribution chain known as "Network of multilateral collaborative partnerships (also known as ecosystems)" (Beth, Chris & Simon, 2017)

Satisfaction The importance of the study of physical satisfaction is the initial factor. Leading to the emotional satisfaction factor and the next is the ability to respond (Demands) that result in the customer to choose the product.

Therefore, knowledge of both physical satisfaction and Emotional Satisfaction factor, which this emotional response is comparable to Marketing demand It then leads to recognition of brand value and customer loyalty. To design products to meet the satisfaction. It must arise from the study of a complete understanding of the customer. The starting point is the customer's needs for any level of physical needs to be satisfied. This level of satisfaction results in the resulting chain of results known as "Value chain", such as emotional satisfaction Perceived Brand Value, Recall, Recognition, Awareness, Brand Equity and Brand Royalty. Emotional Satisfaction means. Jorge (2015) explains that from a marketing and distribution perspective, Emotion Satisfaction that can be obtained from the consumption of products. In the consumer dimension Is the feature of the product / service with 3 parts: symbolic Image of use symbolic image Image of use And emotional image The physical satisfaction is given by the symbolic and the function of the product, while the emotional satisfaction can be caused by the symbol, such as the brand that people accept, use, and user feel. In the acceptance of society Or may be the use For example using a safe product, there will be a feeling of satisfaction which is physical and mental satisfaction. Or in the case of using products that do not cause pollution Users will have a sense of self-worth. In the context of physical and mental product responses, it can be described with the Business Model Canvas, which is used in strategic management. In terms of business, it must be responsive to providing value for money. Customers Purchasing Value Propositions at Physical and Emotional Levels by Osterwalder (2004)

Jukka. el at., (2013) Explain that customers have physical satisfaction in each situation, have different priorities, and are often associated with values and behaviors. Having a deep understanding of the client's needs can be helpful in helping with the design process. By using appropriate technology to produce properties that are suitable for the needs of the product use. Past research studies have often divided marketing data into primary and secondary data. Primary information is information that is collected for a specific purpose, while secondary information refers to information currently available that can be used to enhance marketing knowledge. How to collect customer needs and preferences to improve and develop products and services are as follows: interview, observation, questionnaire collection. In this regard, interviewing customers to develop products can meet the needs of consumers the most. Other than this Strategic Customer Engagement Marketing Customer Experience Management is to encourage customers to be a co-creator of the product. (Co-producer / Co-Creator), which relies on good interaction between customers and the company.

Brand value from a merchant perspective Brand value can be measured by the brand leveraging of a competitor's brand (Aaker, 1991), meaning a strong brand is recognized by merchants. Distributor and extensive distribution of that brand Will make consumers know Familiar with that brand as well As a result, the power to negotiate with customers and distributors. As well as being allocated a good space to place products in the shop of the dealer or distributor.

Brand value from the consumer perspective (Consumer - Based Brand Equity)

Keller (1998) defined the term Brand value in the minds of consumers That is the result of knowledge about the brand (Brand Knowledge) of consumers who respond to the marketing activities (Marketing Response) of the brand, which will be different. The brand value from the consumer perspective is a result of the consumer's positive attitude towards the brand. Attitude is defined as a connection between something that is relevant, related to a brand, in which the consumer evaluates the stimulus in his / her memory. Therefore, the measurement of brand value must be measured from the consumer's attitude towards the brand, which is an important factor affecting consumer purchasing behavior. The added value of the brand will increase the confidence in making purchasing decisions. Increase the level of satisfaction in using the product It also makes it easier to process a large amount of information about a consumer's product. Importance of Brand Value Farquhar (1989) has stated that brand value is It is added value to the company, store or consumer. This is the relationship between branding and customer behavior that affects the sales of products of various companies or organizations. Brand value can be measured through increased cash flow with the presence of all branded products. This is the result of setting a price higher than its competitors. (Premium Pricing) Cost reduction in marketing promotion activities And the increase in market share (Incremental Cash Flow) goal of adding value to the brand. There are two main reasons for this: to allow businesses to set a price for a brand if a deal occurs. To add intangible assets to the balance sheet. In addition, brand value is beneficial to the business of producing and distributing new products. And help in brand management for flexibility If an entity is in crisis, it also acts as a protection against new competitors entering the market (Kotler, 2012).

VI. The conceptual framework gained from the study.

From the sequence of steps, the relationship of the elements that affect the development of brand value. As shown in the order above Able to synthesize results as a conceptual framework Developing product brand value in response to customer satisfaction Participation in building And customer experience management, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Conceptual framework of product brand value development in the dimension of customer satisfaction Participation in building and customer experience management

Source: from literature review Related theories and synthesis as a conceptual framework

VII. Sum up.

Implementing a conceptual framework for meeting customer satisfaction. To develop the brand value of the product to happen It must contain important factors: Responding to customer satisfaction on the part of support by achieving physical satisfaction And emotional satisfaction Another important issue that marketers must pay attention to is development success. Especially if the product cannot show its identity. Making the product not much different Competitive advantages can therefore make a difference in the perception of consumers. For the reason that there are many competitors and the ability of technology to produce results in physical product characteristics that can be similar or identical (Epstein, 2007; Varian, 2006), thus making physical differences. To the product is difficult to do the fact that products can be easily imitated This makes creating an identity and intangible difference a problem. Therefore, the approach developed later is Emotional creation of product identity for customers such as Perceived Value, Brand Awareness and Brand Recognition (Fader & Hardie, 2007; Epstein & Yuthas), 2007) in order for customers / consumers to keep these things in mind, which becomes the behavior of buying that brand.

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